

Original Article

INFLUENCE OF MENTORSHIP ON MANAGERIAL AND DIGITAL COMMUNICATION SKILL DEVELOPMENT OF PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL VICE PRINCIPALS FOR EFFECTIVE SCHOOL MANAGEMENT SUCCESSION IN ENUGU STATE

AGBO, CHINYERE CHARITY, EZEYI VICTORIA and EZEABI I.C. (PHD)

^{1,2}Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education, Faculty of Education, Enugu State University Of Science and Technology (Esut),
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434803>

Abstract

Mentoring is a veritable strategy for human resource management, yet little is known about its effect on employee's performance in school business. This research critically investigated the influence of mentorship on the managerial and digital communication skill development of vice principal's effective performance in private secondary school in Enugu State. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The population used for the study comprised of 395 vice principals in administration cadre of private secondary school. There were no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. This instrument used for the data collection was 20 items questionnaire grouped into to section according to the research questions that guided the study. The items were structured in four-point rating scale. The instrument was validated and reliability of the instrument determined using Crumbach Alpha which yielded 0.85. Out of the 395 copies distributed, 355 copies were returned giving 90.33% return rate. Mean and Standard deviation and t-test statistics were the statistical tools used. The finding of this study revealed that mentoring influences the development of managerial skills ($x=2.91$) and digital communication skills ($x=3.07$) of private secondary schools' principals for effective performance in school management succession. The study recommended among others that teachers and employers of labour at various levels should utilise mentorship as identified in the training and development of managerial and digital communication skills for effective management of school business.

Keywords: *Mentorship, Management and Communication Skills, Vice Principals, Private Secondary Schools, Management Succession.*

Introduction

Entrepreneurship Education has become a developer of business mindsets, creating the understanding regarding the influence of leadership on the performance of workers. In the opinions of Mbah and Onoh (2019), one of the major challenges facing business is having the leadership who identifies sustainable approach to improving service delivery and continuity at the exit of the owner by retirement or death. In the report of Onuoha (2013) in Hudson and Hudson (2016), popular Real Estate firm in Aba in Abia State fizzled away immediately after the death of the founder in 2015. More instances are found again with transport firms in Port Harcourt in Rivers State and in Umuahia in Abia state that were abandoned, some went into desolation after the death of the founders. This sad report and experience showed that an entrepreneurship cannot possibly survive at the retirement of the founder unless the workers were properly coached or mentored on the job.

Entrepreneurship in this context, is the ability and willingness of an individual to seek out business opportunity with good plans of sustaining it for maximum profit. In Onoh's (2013) view, this individual who is willing should have the ability to initiate, control, and direct the processes of production of goods and services and bearing the risks. His entrepreneurial activities cannot be actualized without the acquisition and the utilization of the required skills. In the views of Abanya (2014), entrepreneurial skill or abilities are actions applied by the individual which enables him to identify opportunities, promote and establish business enterprise, aggregate the limited resources required for the production and distribution of goods and services. This ability helps him in organizing, managing human and material resources for the attainment of enterprise objectives, and learning to take the business risks.

Supporting the above opinions, Jegede, Ojo-Ajibere and Aitokhuehi, (2013) viewed skills as developed abilities, or proficiency in performing a task or function, the ability of an entrepreneur of a school to plan, organize, coordinate, sensitize, encourage, source and manage funds, develop the human relationship for effective performance of workers on their jobs. Hence, in a private secondary school system, the vice principal is expected to implement the curriculum and manage the affairs of the school, exhibit innovative leadership skills, be creative in adopting and adapting to both the government policies and other global changes that affect school business for its continuity.

In Nigerian educational system, the Nigeria Policy in education (FRN, 2013) grouped educational system into tertiary, secondary, primary and the Nursery. Each of these institutions is either public institutions owed by the government or private institutions or by individuals, organizations or religious bodies. On the general, an individual, group of persons or religious body may decide to establish and manage a private secondary school that aligns with their religious beliefs, cultural values and economic status that differ from government owned public schools. Some of these their objectives include enjoyment of autonomy and independence, operating independently in order to make decisions on curriculum, teaching methods, religious and cultural beliefs, languages and finally making policies without much government interference (National Association of Independent Schools, 2019). Achieving these objectives enables them to provide higher quality education with better resources, have manageable class sizes with more qualified teachers, have facilities that matches the emerging technology, libraries, and sport facilities. As change makers, through innovation and specialization, private schools innovate and specialize in specific areas as in arts, music, vocational trainings, science and special needs, which may not be readily

available in government schools, they mostly offer safer, more academically secured environment, and directly accountable to parents.

According to Federal Republic of Nigeria National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), in her National Policy on Education, secondary education is a level of education where children receive education after primary education and before the tertiary stage, whose goals among others include:

- Providing primary school leavers with the opportunity for education at a higher level, irrespective of sex, social status, religious or ethnic backgrounds,
- offering diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities for future role,
- developing and promoting Nigerian languages, arts and culture in the context of cultural heritage,
- inspiring students with desire for self-improvement,
- fostering national unity with emphasis on the common ties that unite citizens in their diversity, respect the views and feelings of others with respect to dignity of labour,
- appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals and live as good citizens and finally
- Provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development. It should be noted that these objectives may not be properly achieved in private schools without mentoring the staff whose duties are to implement them.

Mentorship in this aspect covers all activities that prove support to a less experienced person to acquire the skills and abilities needed for expert's performance. Mentorship according to Frank (2018) provides support and collaborative teaching environment that help teachers, students and less experienced staff to develop into more confident, self-

directed independent staff or teacher. On manpower development, mentorship provide the workforce required in stimulating innovation, cultivating creativity in business, empowering diverse range of employees that share new opinions, ideas, knowledge and experience on a level playing ground. Mentorship not only help the private schools develop and retain talented staff but helps in building a robust community of diverse teachers for nation building (Francis 2019). According to University of Washington (2020), mentorship is usually a long-term process, driven by mentees and goes beyond the traditional role of student and teacher in classroom, and it is normally a two-way communication process. As an educational expert, Friedman (2020) explained that the school proprietors and proprietresses employ the service of an experienced principal with special qualities of school administration, who in turn appoints an assistant known as the vice principal to work with him in the daily management of the school activities, in order to achieve the goals of the school. A private secondary school with few students may just have a vice principal for general administration while a large school may have different vice principals on administration, on academics, on special duties as the case may be.

However, the effective performance of this vice principal who would effectively succeed the principal depends on the degree of knowledge of managerial and digital skills acquired while under-studying or being mentored by the principal. Through mentorship, the vice principal develops the operational skills that enable him to plan school activities and its achievement strategies. This planning strategies help him to organize programs, direct work, lead others, motivate workers, and coordinate all schools' activities. For him to utilise these attributes, he must have the interest of the school at heart, be intelligent, have the abilities, be resilient towards challenges, action oriented, prudent in spending money,

maintaining and willing to take calculated risks (Francis,2019).As the financial manager of the school, he must know how to keep all accounting records such as the cheque books, receipt and invoice books, ledgers to keep the tracks of the financial flows of the school(Sam,2017)Digitalisation in its own side has become important and is rapidly influencing all aspects of business life, and school business not an exception. School digital communication strategies are found in audio-visual contents, soft wares, and hard wares. These strategies have helped in enhancing communication among the schools and the stakeholders, improving collaboration and information sharing, streamlining process, providing access to data that informs decision making, personalising learning for students' engagement in study and supporting teachers training and development(Bloom, 2019).In another development, Ikeanyionwu and Enwere (2019),noted that not only are teachers critical variables that need mentoring for educational development, they are the most significant education transformation agents, hence need broad knowledge on digital communication skills. According to Adebayo (2019), this emergence of technological advancement and the migration from analogue to digital has resulted to an increase in the production and utilization of electronic gadgets like the computers, information and communication devices or High-Tec equipment. The high definition television sets, wireless electronic cameras, and digital recording devices, unnamed vehicle cameras, visual reality gargets and artificial intelligence among other emerging technologies have become an integral part of life, guaranteeing safety, good health, happiness, satisfaction, work efficiency and effectiveness of individuals, group or team -work in an organization. Still on Adebayo, digital communication skill knowledge is a transferable skill needed by a worker to make him suitable, employable

and effective in adapting to the 21-century school business.

It is evident as agreed therefore by Amaiya (2016) that the traditional educational environments are not suitable for preparing students to function or be productive in the workplace in today's society without digital transformation, hence Lehman (2014) asserts that for school to succeed in digital transformation, the vice principal of a school must undergo a cultural change through proper mentoring on the use of internet facilities, computers, and ancillaries such as the social media, digital display adverts, Online world webs, videos mobile phone.

In the mentoring relationship, the vice principal utilizes oral and written communication skills, team-oriented skills, leadership skills, one-one methods to achieve the purpose. As no single mentor provides all the forms of mentoring a potential successor needs, the teacher mentees are encouraged to have a multiple mentor to transfer the knowledge (Lunsford and Barker, 2017). In a secondary school system, mentorship should be a developmental relationship in which a more experienced and knowledge principal helps, guides, instructs, counsels and facilitates the intellectual and career development of the less experienced teachers or vice principals for an effective leadership role, and a successful approach to preparation of technique for future skilled workforce (Adebayo, 2019). In Hudson (2013) point of view, mentorship should involve the exchange of wisdom, learning, development of skill, gaining knowledge about the organization, achieved through modelling, coaching, counselling, advocacy and networking. As the vice principals are under the leadership of the principal in secondary schools, these mentoring skills help the vice principal develop more leadership competencies in school management and to adapt to any cultural, religion, government policies that may affect school progress and continuity. It is expected that at the exit of a principal, the vice principal if

mentored can succeed the principal in effective management of school.

Management of private secondary school according to Ezeabii (2016) anyway is not the same in totality with the management of government-owned schools. The author noted that while the private schools are established, approved by the government, financed, managed by individual(s) known as proprietors (Male) or Proprietress (female) or by a hired principal, the government schools are established, funded, managed by government bodies through the Ministries and statutory boards for education. This difference lies in the components as stipulated in the National policy guideline (FRN.2014) such as Junior (upper basic) and senior secondary schools. Nevertheless, the management of the private secondary schools are not gender biased, as any gender with interest, competence can own or manage a private secondary school in Enugu State.

Gender from Ironkwe's(2014) point of view is the quality and traits associated with male and female in the society, characterized from their daily activities, lives and behaviours. This means that each vice principal in leadership position whether male or female must have the ability to mentor workers in order to improve performance. This notwithstanding, Agu (2010) pinioned that some communities, cultures and religion still places different roles to gender, relegating house chore roles to women, thereby preventing them from going to school, placing them on disadvantaged position in family business. But Shane (2000) and Shaidu (2010) in Ezedum (2011) in their own view, stated that many women in recent time in Nigeria have broken themselves off from those past experiences of degraded discriminations and have become entrepreneurs. In Enugu State for an instance, women like Mrs. Joy Ezilo founded and established the Women Aid Collective (WACOL) and Mrs. Asogwa founded the Development Education Centre for women Empowerment among others. Most

of them have become owners of private schools as proprietors (Male) and proprietresses (Females), promoting different kinds of business, and as social agents solicits the partnership of other persons as partners or principal who initiates, plan, and coordinate the activities of secondary schools, who also has the potentials and skills of being able to identify opportunities, where the ordinary man see threats and failures. This principal with approval of the founder appoints an experienced teacher to work as assistant, generally known as a vice principal, under his mentorship assists in overseeing the daily management of the school, (who could either be male or female,) for his adoption and adaptation to the 21st century leadership strategies for private secondary school business and its continuity as propounded by Collins Brown and Newman (1998) on Cognitive Apprenticeship and the Self- determination theory strategies by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan (1980). There views on autonomy, competence and relatedness, have helped mentors establish the psychological needs that drives proper mentorship for effective work performance of the vice principals.

However, this generational transition from the founder of the private school to a successor has lots of challenging issues in which most school founders or owners found succession difficult because of its complexities thereby, making the mistakes of not having proper arrangement or programme of mentoring the incumbent principal who would cascade the experience to a possible successor. They make more mistakes of not distinguishing between business ownership, governance and its management, not seeing succession program as a continuous activity rather than as thing of the past, and as a process, nor an opportunity for the future thereby causing a collapse on the continuity of school and its management.

Statement of the Problem.

Inefficiency in employee's performance could be caused by a mismatch between skills learned in the school and the application of such skills in running a business (Ezeabii, 2016). As a result of this gap, the appointed vice principal who was never coached nor mentored uses his head knowledge to perform works that demand special skills and tactics. This results to inefficiency, ineffective in handling difficult business challenges, and could be declared redundant when he is not capable of taking up the management of the business at the exit of his predecessor. More so with this global increase in school business, emphasis should be laid on empowering the vice principals on most important school leadership skills with regards to management and digital communication skills through mentorship. (Sam, 2017). It is against this background that the study examines the influence of mentorship on managerial and digital communication skills development of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school succession in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to determine the influence of mentorship on managerial and digital communication skill development of the vice principals of private secondary school effective performance for management succession in Enugu State.

Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. Influence of mentorship in developing managerial skills of private secondary schools' vice principals for effective performance school management succession in Enugu State
- 2 Influence of mentorship in developing digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school management succession in Enugu State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the influences of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private secondary schools' vice principals for effective performance in management succession in Enugu State?
2. What are the influences of mentorship in developing digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in management succession in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following null hypotheses were tested at 05 level of significance.

Ho1: A significant difference does not exist between the mean scores of male and female respondents with respect to the influence of mentorship in developing managerial skills of vice principals of private secondary schools for effective performance in management succession in Enugu State.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean score of the male and female respondents with respect to the influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of vice principals of private secondary schools for effective performance in management succession in Enugu State

Research Method

The study was carried out in Enugu State. Population for the study comprised of 395 vice principal's administration of private secondary schools in the six educational zones of Enugu State, Nigeria. Due to the manageable size, there were no sampling. The instrument for the data collection was a structured four-point scale questionnaire developed by the researcher titled influence of mentorship on managerial and digital skills development of vice principals of private secondary schools for effective performance in Enugu State. The instruments had two parts,(1&2).Part 1 was on bio data (gender)while part two had two sections(A&B).Section 'A' with 14 items elicited responses on influence of mentorship on managerial skills development of principals of private

secondary schools for effective performance in schools management succession .Section ‘B’ with nine items elicited responses on influence of digital communication skills development of private secondary schools vice principals for effective performance in school management succession.

The questionnaire items were validated by three experts. While the internal consistency method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument using a pilot test. Data collected were analysed using Crumbach Alpha and it yielded an overall coefficient of 0.83 indicating that the was reliable.

Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents in their schools with the help of four 4 research assistance dully briefed on what to do and the method to be used. On – the – spot method was used in administration but respondents who were ready with their responses were followed up on phone for possible time of visiting for collection. Out of the 395 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 355 copies were properly filled and collated, representing 90.33% return rate.

Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research question and check the closeness of respondents’ response. The decision was based on the overall cluster mean ratings in relation to the upper and lower limit of the mean. The

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation on the influence of mentorship in developing managerial skills of vice principals for effective performance in school management succession in Enugu State.

N 355

S/N	Influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession include ability to:	Male N = 165		Female N=190		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	Develop good administrative know-how	2.98	0.74	3.02	0.76	2.99	0.75	Agree
2	Ensure order and discipline in work place	3.02	0.71	3.07	0.72	3.05	0.71	Agree
3	Develop ability to properly monitor teaching and learning	3.08	0.65	3.11	0.69	3.10	0.67	Agree
4	Develop school vision and mission statement	2.95	0.73	2.99	0.74	2.97	0.73	Agree

analysis was conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance using t-test, upper and lower limit of the mean was used to determine the degree of agreement of the respondents to each research questions thus:

Strongly agree		(SA)
	3.50-4.00	
Agree		(A)
	2.50-3.49	
Disagree		(DA)
	1.50-2.49	
Strongly disagree		(SD)
	1.00-1.49	

The null hypothesis as significant where the two tails significant value was less than or equal to 0.5 significant level at appropriate degree of freedom, otherwise the null hypothesis was not significant.

Data collected and analyzed were presented in Tables according to the research questions that guided the study and the hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1

What are the influences of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private secondary school’s vice principals for effective performance in school management succession in Enugu State?

5	Develop the ability for effective negotiation of salaries and fees	2.88	0.79	2.95	0.80	2.92	0.79	Agree
6	Develop the ability for establishing strategies for achievement of goals	2.90	0.74	2.94	0.72	2.92	0.73	Agree
7	Develop ability for conflict resolution at workplace	2.88	0.78	2.94	0.75	2.92	0.76	Agree
8	Develop ability for work evaluation	2.76	0.77	2.83	0.74	2.79	0.76	Agree
9	Develop competency in staff recruitment	2.82	0.81	2.87	0.79	2.85	0.08	Agree
10	Develop the competency for school establishment	2.79	0.75	2.85	0.74	2.82	0.75	Agree
11	Develop ability to retain patronages	2.84	0.78	2.86	0.77	2.85	0.77	Agree
12	Develop the spirit of innovation in school business	2.76	0.73	2.74	0.69	2.75	0.71	Agree
13	Develop the ability to organize, coordinate and motivate workers for improved performance	2.87	0.72	2.83	0.69	2.85	0.70	Agree
14	Develop the ability for the establishment of rules and regulations governing school business	2.93	0.69	2.87	0.66	2.90	0.67	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		2.89	0.74	2.92	0.73	2.91	0.74	Agree

X= Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

The data presented in Table 1 indicates that overall them item mean scores ranges from 2.75 to 3.10 depicting agree. This shows that the items are the influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The overall cluster means score 2.91 indicate agree. This implies that the itemized are the influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The low standard deviation of 0.74 shows that

the respondent's opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized.

Hypothesis 1

A significant difference does not exist between the mean scores in mentorship between the female and males on managerial skills of private school vice principals for effective performance in management succession in Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of mean scores of female and male respondents on managerial skills development of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

Variables	N	T	Df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	165	527	355	598	-40702	.77211	NS
Female	190						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 598 degree of freedom for the items is 0.527 with a significant of 0.598. As the significant value of 0.598 is more than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean rating in mentorship between the female and male on managerial skills development of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school management succession in Enugu State.

Research Question 2

What are the influences of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State?

Table 3: Mean response and standard deviation on the influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

N 355

S/N	Influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession includes:	Male N= 165		Female N=190		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
15	Developing the ability to utilize audio-visual technology from teaching and learning process	3.18	0.73	3.17	0.70	3.17	0.71	Agree
16	Develop the ability to utilize stream charts for teaching and learning	3.23	0.64	3.22	0.60	3.23	0.62	Agree
17	Develop the use of word processor for teaching and learning	3.08	0.76	3.06	0.77	3.07	0.76	Agree
18	Develop the use of power point for teaching and learning	3.10	0.78	3.09	0.78	3.10	0.78	Agree
19	Ability to provide instruction through instant massaging	3.03	0.73	3.02	0.74	3.02	0.73	Agree
20	Ability to provide instruction through digital videos	3.02	0.70	3.02	0.69	3.02	0.70	Agree
21	Ability to utilize Online facilities for communication	3.07	0.68	3.08	0.64	3.08	0.66	Agree
22	Ability to utilize email, phone calls to promote performance	3.04	0.67	3.06	0.61	3.05	0.64	Agree
23	Promote the use of e-commerce facilities for payment of fees and salaries	2.89	0.62	2.90	0.57	2.90	0.59	Agree
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.07	0.70	3.06	0.68	3.07	0.68	Agree

X=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation

The analysis of data presented in Table 3 above shows that the mean scores of the items range from 2.90 to 3.23 indicating that the respondents agree to the itemized as the influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The overall cluster mean of 3.07 also depicts agree. The standard deviation of 0.68 shows that the respondents have homogeneity in their responses to the items as the influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

Variables	N	t	Df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	165	.095	355	.924	.04561	.47930	NS
Female	190						

The result of data analysis from the t-test in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 355 degree of freedom for the items is 0,095 with a significant value of 0.924. Since the significant value of 0.924 is more than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean rating of the male and female on mentorship for digital communication skills development of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The findings according to research question two depicted the influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between the mean scores of the male and female respondents on the influence of mentoring on digital communication skills development of private school vice principal’s performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean scores of the male and female respondents influence of mentoring on digital communication skills development of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

The findings according to research question one identified the influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of private school vice principal’s effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The study showed that the influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills includes the ability to: develop good administrative know-how, ensure order and discipline in work place, develop ability to properly monitor teaching and learning develop school vision and mission statement, develop the ability for effective negotiation of salaries and fees, develop the ability for establishing strategies for achievement of goals, develop ability for conflict resolution at workplace, and develop ability for work evaluation. It also includes the ability to develop competency in staff recruitment, develop the competency for school establishment, develop ability to retain patronages

and develop the spirit of innovation in school business, develop the ability to organize, coordinate and motivate workers for improved performance and develop the ability for the establishment of rules and regulation governing school business. The identified influence of mentorship on the development of managerial skills are supported by Sam (2017), who noted that paternalistic style of family business is often considered to be autocratic, in that the manager make decisions and imposes them on employees. This indicated that the identified points showed the influence mentorship has in the development of the managerial skills of business education student's for efficient performance in family business.

Furthermore, the finding of study indicated that a significant difference does not exist between the mean scores in mentorship between the male and female respondents on managerial skills development of private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The implication of no significant different was that gender had no significant impact on the identified influence of mentorship in developing the managerial skills of employees for effective performance in family business.

The findings of the study on question two also indicated the influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills of private secondary schools vice principals s effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The digital communication skills of private secondary school vice principals' effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State. The identified influence of mentorship in developing the digital communication skills include; develop the ability to utilize audio-visual technology for teaching and learning process, develop the ability to utilize stream charts for teaching and learning, develop the use of word processor for

teaching and learning, develop the use of power point for teaching and learning ability to provide instruction through instant messaging ability to provide instruction through digital videos, ability to utilize online facilities for communication, ability to utilize email, phone calls to promote performance and promote the use of e-commerce facilities for payment of fees and salaries. The result of this study showed that mentorship influences the development of these digital Communication skills. The findings of the study were in line with Mumuni and Sam (2014) that the general contribution of ICT to business helps and assists the vice principals in Enugu State apply the intellectual tools and practical experience to update the new knowledge, skills. Microsoft office skills knowledge would also help in handling office machines for self-reliance when acquired through this mentoring relationship. Ololube(2016) stated that skills in the use of hardware devices of a computer system are highly needed for effective instructional delivery for achieving sustainable schools business goals in Enugu State.

Furthermore, the findings of the study indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean score of the male and female respondents on mentorship for digital communication skills development for private secondary school vice principals for effective performance in school family business management succession in Enugu State. The gender of the respondents had no influence on the identified of mentorship in development the digital communication skills of vice principals for effective performance in school business management succession in Enugu State.

Conclusion

The study determined the influence of mentorship on the development of managerial and digital communication skills among school's vice principals for effective performance in school business. By this identification, it depicted that proper training of

employees or vice principals through mentorship would provide for effective management of school business. Hence, mentorship may be used to improve the employees and employers during their industrial attachment programmers for effective management school business for sustainability and that Principals, the teachers at all levels, entrepreneurs and the government are expected to utilize mentorship in the development of managerial and digital communication skills for effective management succession of family business. This is necessary as there is need to achieve the desired growth, development and sustainability in the employees and student's performance while establishing and managing family businesses.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Teachers and employers of labour at various levels should utilize mentorship as identified in the training and development of managerial and communication skills for effective management of school business.
2. The government and concerned bodies in education should empower the teachers in the use of mentorship as a training tool for entrepreneurial skills development of the students for effective succession.
3. In-service training should be organized on the need for effective utilization of mentorship as an effective tool for entrepreneurial skill development for business sustainability in Enugu State.

Reference

Abanya, F.E (2014). Self-employment skills possessed by Business Education Students of Collage of Education for sustainable development in Cross Rivers; Unpublished M.ed. Thesis University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Adebayo, A.M (2019). Training of office Technology and Management Education students for job demands and self-employment in Ekiti State. *Journal of Advance Studies in Social Science*.

Amaiya, A.O (2016). Availability and Initialization of New Technology for teaching office technology and management in Delta State Polytechnic Nigeria. *Journal of Business Education*, 3(2), 64-72.

Bloom, H (2020). Digitalization in Education. A review of Literature, *Journal of educational Technology and Exchange*. 13(1) 1-23.

Edokpolor .J.E and Egbri .J.N. (2017). Business education in Nigeria for value-orientation: A strategic approach to poverty alleviation and national development *Journal of Educational Research and Review* 5(2) A-48.

Ezeabii 1C (2016). Entrepreneurship planning and organizational skills needed by Business Education Students in public universities in South-East State in Nigeria for self-employment. *Association of Business Education in conference proceedings* 3(1), 398-408.

Ezedum C E; Agbo, Fu; Odugbo GO (2011). *Introduction to Entrepreneurship*. Publication of the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Development Research (CEDR). University of Nigeria Nsukka.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013/14) *National Policy on Education* Lagos NERDC press.

Francis. L (2019). Need help developing soft skills? Get a mentor from <https://www.learningofficer.com/2017/01/helps-developing-soft-skill-set-mentor>.

- Frank, L. (2018). Online Mentoring: How technology can enhance mentoring connections. Retrieved from <https://11chronus.com/blog/online-mentoring-how-technology-can-enhance-mentoring-connections>.
- Hudson p (2013). Mentoring as professional development. Growth for both mentor and mentees. *Professional Development in Education*. 39(5) 771-783 doi 10.1080/19415257201274945.
- Hudson, D and Hudson, S (2016) Mentoring Beginning Teachers Education. 4(10), 48-62. [Http://dox.doi.org/10.14211/ajt,2016.v41.no10.4](http://dox.doi.org/10.14211/ajt,2016.v41.no10.4).
- Ironkwe AG (2011) in Mba, GO (2019). Analysis of Gender and Household Food Production and Security in South-East, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis on Development of Agricultural Economics and Technology, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT).
- Jegede, O.I, Ojo – Ajibare J.O and Aitokhuehi O.O (2013) Entrepreneurship Education through higher Education in Nigeria, *Journal of Education Reviews* 5(2), 209-216
- Lehman, R.M and Concieno, S.C (2014). Motivating and retaining online students. Research based strategies that work. John Wiley and Sons.
- Lunsford, L.G and Barker.V. (2016). Great Mentoring in graduate school: A quick start guide for protégées. Council of Graduate Schools. 4.
- Margratte, R (2019). What is Survey Research? Research from <https://www.techterms.com/definition/survey> research 12.03-2019.10:30am.
- Mba, CN (2016) Utilizing ICT in teaching and learning programme of Collage of Education in Kaduna Learner, perception. *Journal of Research and Development* 2(1) 78-87.
- Mununi, I.A and Sam, A.H (2014). Modern office Technology and the Performance of the Professional Sedentary in Contemporary Organizations in Ghana; *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 3(4).
- National Association of Independent Schools (NAIS, 2019) Mentorships and Leadership Development in Schools.
- Nwokike, F.O, Ezeabii. IC; and Jim E.U (2018). Business Education; an Indispensable tool for achieving sustainable development in the South-East in Nigeria *British Journal of Education*, 6(1), 19-27.
- Ololude N.P (2016). The Impact of Professional and non-professional Teachers ICT competences in Secondary schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Information and Technology Impact*, 6(2), 101-118.
- Onoh BCEC (2013). Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship studies. Enugu Cheston Agency press Ltd Enugu.
- Onwuasoanya, B.U, and Ejezie C.I (2020). Perception of teachers in proliferation of primary schools in Anambra State, *Lafia Journal of Education* ISSN 2714-514 x Vol 1. 2020.

University of Washington (2020) Mentoring: A guide for faculty. <https://grad.uni.edu/for-students-an-posvdoc/coreprograms/mentoring/mentoring-a-guide-for-faculty>

Uzoagulu, AE (2013). Practical to Writing Research in Testacy Insinuation Enugu John Jacobs Classic Publishers Ltd.